

Supplementary Table S6. Species used in analysis, here listed with diel activity (i.e., light regime: 1, observed active during both the night and the day; 0, observed active during the day only) as inferred from published field observation records (see reference list below table) and/or museum collection data: NHMUK – Natural History Museum, London, UK; MNHN – Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; UF – Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, USA; AORI – Atmosphere and Ocean Research Institute, University of Tokyo, Japan; NTM – Museum and Art Gallery of the Northern Territory, Darwin, Australia; NMNH – Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, USA; NTM – Natuurhistorisch Museum Rotterdam, Netherlands. Justifications given here for state attributed to each species; see methods for further details.

Species	Diel activity	Justification	Reference
<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>	1	Collected at night (20:20)	NHMUK
<i>Aporrhais serresiana</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Rimellopsis laurenti</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Rostellariella delicatula</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Tibia insulaechorab</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	UF
<i>Varicospira cancellata</i>	1	Collected during night dive	NMR
<i>Terebellum delicatum</i>	1	Collected at night; photos taken during night dives	Abbott, 1962. Photos at: Blatterer and Blatterer, 2019; http://www.diverrosa.com
<i>Terebellum terebellum C</i>	1		
<i>Canarium darwinense</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NTM
<i>Canarium erythrinum</i>	1	Collected at night; photos taken during night dives	MNHN. Photo: Blatterer and Blatterer, 2019
<i>Canarium incisum</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN
<i>Canarium labiatum</i>	1	Collected at night	NHMUK
<i>Canarium olydium</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NHMUK
“ <i>Canarium</i> ” <i>wilsonorum</i> A	1	Collected at night	Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Paul Merrill
<i>Conomurex decorus</i>	1	Collected at night	Kronenberg et al., 2008
<i>Conomurex fasciatus</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Conomurex luhuanus</i>	1	Collected at night; behavioural observations; photos taken during night dives	MNHN; Kuwamura et al., 1983; Maxwell et al. 2021. Photo: https://www.diverrosa.com
<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NHMUK

<i>Euprotomus aurisdianae</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	MNHN; NMR
<i>Euprotomus bulla</i>	1	Collected at night; photos taken during night dives	MNHN; Maxwell et al., 2021. Photos: Wieneke et al., taken by Magdalena Fischhuber; https://www.diverosa.com
<i>Fusistrombus fusiformis</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	MNHN
<i>Gibberulus gibberulus</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN; NMNH; UF; Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Christian Börnke
<i>Gibberulus gibbosus</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN; Maxwell et al., 2021; Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Paul Merrill
<i>Harpago chiragra</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NHMUK
<i>Labiostrombus labiosus</i>	1	Collected at night, and deep (> 200 m)	Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Ulrich Wieneke
<i>Labiostrombus pulchellus</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Labiostrombus robustus</i>	1	Photos taken during night dives	Photo: https://www.diverosa.com
<i>Labiostrombus turturella</i> B	0	Hand-collected during day	MNHN
<i>Labiostrombus variabilis</i>	1	Collected at night; behavioural observations	MNHN; Maxwell et al., 2021; Wieneke et al., 2022, pers. comm. Jeanette and Scott Johnson
<i>Labiostrombus vittatus</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Labiostrombus wienekei</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Gijs Kronenberg
<i>Lambis lambis</i> A	0	Hand-collected during day	MNHN
<i>Lambis lambis</i> B	0	Hand-collected during day	NHMUK
<i>Lambis robusta</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Lambis scorpius</i>	1	Collected during night dive	NMR
<i>Lambis truncata</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Latissistrombus taurus</i>	1	Collected during night dive	Wieneke et al. 2022, coll. Christian Börnke
<i>Lentigo lentiginosus</i>	1	Collected at night; photos taken during night dives	Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Richard Salisbury. Photos: https://www.diverosa.com
<i>Lentigo pipus</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN; Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Guido Poppe
<i>Lentigo thersites</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Lobatus raninus</i>	1	Behavioural observations	Seyer, 1994
<i>Maculastrombus microunceus</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN; Maxwell et al., 2021
<i>Maculastrombus mutabilis</i> B	1	Collected at night	UF; Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Christian Börnke

<i>Ministrombus minimus</i>	1	Collected at night	Wieneke et al., 2022, coll. Koenraad De Turck
<i>Ophioglossolambis digitata</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Strombus pugilis</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Terestrombus terebellatus</i>	1	Collected at night	MNHN
<i>Thetystrombus latus</i>	1	Collected during night dive	NMR
<i>Tricornis tricornis</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMR
<i>Tridentarius dentatus</i>	1	Collected at night; photos taken during night dives	UF. Photo: Wieneke et al., 2022, taken by Bob Abela
<i>Pellicaria vermis</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Struthiolaria papulosa</i>	0	Hand-collected during day	NMNZ; AORI
<i>Onustus caribaeus</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Xenophora conchyliophora</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Xenophora pallidula</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2
<i>Xenophora solarioides</i>	1	Deep (> 200 m)	See Supplementary Table S2

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